

Relative Intensity Noise of Vertical-Cavity Surface-Emitting Lasers Subject to Variable Polarization-Optical Feedback

Authors : Salam Nazhan Ahmed

Abstract : Influence of variable polarization angle (θ_p) of optical feedback on the Relative Intensity Noise (RIN) of a Vertical-Cavity Surface-Emitting Laser (VCSEL) has been experimentally investigated. The RIN is a minimum at $\theta_p = 0^\circ$ for the dominant polarization mode (XP), and at $\theta_p = 90^\circ$ for the suppressed polarization mode (YP) of VCSEL. Furthermore, the RIN of the XP mode increases rapidly with increasing θ_p , while for the YP mode, it increases slightly to $\theta_p = 45^\circ$ and decreases for angles greater than 45° .

Keywords : lasers, vertical-cavity surface-emitting lasers, optical switching, optical polarization feedback, relative intensity noise

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